

Supplementary File 6: Photoplethysmography Results

In order to regress the blood-pulse volume recorded with the photoplethysmograph sensor, an independent component (IC) analysis was conducted on the raw *f*NIRS signal for each index (i.e., HbO₂ and HHb). Pearson's correlation coefficient was computed between each of the first 20 ICs and the photoplethysmography signal. The IC exhibiting the highest correlation coefficient was removed from the *f*NIRS signal (i.e., the signal was reconstructed excluding that IC). Details of the correlation coefficients between the removed IC and each designated *f*NIRS index can be found in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for Photoplethysmography Results

Index	Minimum	Maximum	Median	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE</i>
HbO ₂	.025	.502	.148	.174	.101	.010
HHb	.029	.492	.107	.124	.080	.008

Note. HbO₂ = oxygenated hemoglobin; HHb = deoxygenated hemoglobin.